

Supplementary Online Material (SOM):

Dentition of the Mugharet el'Aliya fossil human maxilla, Morocco

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Supplementary Figures

SOM Figure S1: Visualization of intra- and inter-observer error for the UC EDJ dataset. Euclidean distances (ED) are calculated in mm between repeated measurements of the same landmark position. Detailed landmarks definitions are listed in [SOM Table S5](#) and their visualization is shown in [Figure 2b](#).

SOM Figure S2: Visualization of intra- and inter-observer error for the a) UP3 and b) UP4 EDJ datasets. Euclidean distances (ED) are calculated in mm between repeated measurements of the same landmark position. Detailed landmarks definitions are listed in [SOM Table S5](#) and their visualization is shown in [Figure 2a](#).

a) UC

b) UP3

c) UP4

Symbols

- ✱ Error
- ▲ Middle Pleistocene
- Late Pleistocene
- Holocene

Colors

- Error
- later *H. sapiens*
- early *H. sapiens* & Aterian
- *H. neanderthalensis*

SOM Figure S3: EDJ shape PCAs of a) upper permanent canines (UC), b) third (UP3), and c) fourth premolars (UP4) with all repeated error measurements projected into the plots of PC1 against PC2. Abbreviations as in [SOM Table S4](#).

SOM Figure S4: Visualization of crown area (MD*BL) per tooth type. Crown area shown in mm² and tooth types from left to right: UC, UP3 and UP4. Group mean values are illustrated as symbols and standard deviations (sd) as range. Detailed information about the sample in [SOM Table S3](#) and underlying values in [SOM Table S7](#).

SOM Figure S5: Upper permanent canine (UC) shape PCA with Mugharet el'Aliya and all early *H. sapiens* fossils projected into the plot. PC1 plotted against log CS. Symbols, colors, and abbreviations as in Figure 4 and SOM Table S4.

SOM Figure S6: Upper permanent third premolar (UP3) shape PCA with Mugharet el'Aliya and all early *H. sapiens* fossils projected into the plot. PC2 plotted against log CS. Symbols, colors, and abbreviations as in [Figure 4](#) and [SOM Table S4](#).

SOM Figure S7: Upper permanent fourth premolar (UP4) shape PCA with Mugharet el'Aliya and all early *H. sapiens* fossils projected into the plot. PC1 plotted against log CS. Symbols, colors, and abbreviations as in [Figure 4](#) and [SOM Table S4](#).

Supplementary Tables

SOM Table S1: Description of non-metric traits used for the comparison of upper permanent canines (UC), third premolars (UP3), and fourth premolars (UP4). Definitions, grades, and their descriptions are based on [Martín-Torres et al. \(2012\)](#), [Bailey \(2006\)](#), and [Scott & Irish \(2017\)](#).

Tooth Type	Trait	Definition	Grades	Description
UC	Tuberculum dentale	Presence of tubercles, ridges, or cusp-like features expressed in the cingular region of the lingual surface.	0	No expression, resulting in a smooth surface.
			1	Faint ridging
			2	Trace ridging
			3	Strong ridging
			4	Pronounced ridging
			5	Weakly developed cuspule with a free apex.
	Mesial ridge	Relative development of the mesial marginal ridge on the lingual surface compared to the distal ridge.	0	Mesial and distal ridges are the same size and not attached to the tuberculum dentale.
			1	Mesial ridge is larger than the distal and it may be weakly attached to the tuberculum dentale.
			2	Mesial ridge is larger than the distal and is moderately attached to the tuberculum dentale.
	Distal accessory ridge	Ridge development in the distolingual fossa, between the tooth apex and the distolingual marginal ridge.	3	Mesial ridge is much larger and incorporates the tuberculum dentale. (Morris' type.)
			0	The ridge is absent.
			1	The ridge shows a faint expression.
			2	The ridge shows a slight expression.
			3	The ridge shows moderate development.
	Shovel shape	The presence of lingual marginal ridges.	4	The ridge is strongly developed.
5			The ridge is pronounced.	
0			Marginal ridges are not expressed.	
1			Faint shovel shape	
2			Trace of shovel shape. Elevations of the marginal ridges are easily seen.	
UP3, UP4	Essential crest	Presence of the essential crest on the buccal or lingual cusp. Degree of expression and location (buccal/lingual) are scored	3	The ridge shows moderate development.
			4	The ridge is strongly developed.
			5	The ridge is pronounced.
	Accessory ridge (MaxPAR)	The presence of accessory ridges on the buccal cusp. Degree of expression and location (mesial/distal) are scored.	0	Marginal ridges are not expressed.
			1	Faint shovel shape
	Transverse crest	Expression of a transverse crest connecting the main cusps of the premolar.	2	Trace of shovel shape. Elevations of the marginal ridges are easily seen.
			3	Moderate shovel shape
			4	Pronounced shovel shape
	Accessory cusps	The presence of an accessory marginal tubercle in form of a bulge or free-standing accessory tubercle on the marginal ridge. Location (mesial/distal) is scored.	5	Strong shovel shape
			0	The crest is absent.
			1	The crest is present.
			2	The crest is bifurcated.
			0	The ridge is absent.
			1	The ridge is present.
			0	The crest is absent.
			1	The crest is weak or it is interrupted by the sagittal fissure.
			2	The crest is pronounced or the sagittal fissure is erased.
			0	The cusp is absent.
			1	The cusp is present.

SOM Table S2: Sample used in the comparison of non-metric features of upper permanent canines (UC), third premolars (UP3), and fourth premolars (UP4).

Groups		Sites	Source
	early	Jebel Irhoud, Misliya, Qafzeh, Skhul, Sea Harvest, Hoedjies Punt, Klasies River Mouth, Equus Cave, Die Kelders	a-c, e
<i>Homo sapiens</i>	later	Upper Paleolithic individuals from Les Abeilles, Abri Blanchard, Abri Labattut, Abri Pataud, Arcy-sur-Cure, Brno, Dolní Věstonice, Farincourt, Fourneau du Diable, Fontchevade, Grotte des Rois, Gough's Cave, Isturitz, La Chaud, La Ferrassie, La Gravette, La Madeleine, Laugerie-Basse, La Vachons, Miesslingtal, Mladeč, Peștera cu Oase, Oberkassel, Pavlov, Peche de la Boissiere, Roc-de-Combe, Solutré, St. Germain-la-Rivière; Epipaleolithic individuals from North West Africa; Mesolithic and Neolithic individuals from France; recent individuals from globally distributed populations	a, d-e
<i>Homo neanderthalensis</i>		Arcy-sur-Cure (Grotte du Renne, Grotte de l'Hyène, Grotte du Loup, Grotte du Bison), La Quina, Malarnaud, Petit-Puymoyen, Pinilla del Valle, Cabezo Gordo, Engis, Fondo Cattie, Saccopastore, Tabun, Krapina, Le Moustier, Monsempron, Saint-Césaire, Shanidar, Sidrón, Hortus, Grotta Breuil, Monte Fenera, Guattari, Devil's Tower Gibraltar, Regourdou, Roc de Marsal, Taddeo, Melpignano, Combe-Grenal, Vindija, Kůlna, Ochoz, Kebara, Amud, Ehringsdorf, Spy, Shanidar	d-e
Middle Pleistocene	Europe	Arago, Mauer, Mountmarin, Pontnewydd, Steinheim, Petralona, Fonta Ranuccio, Atapuerca-SH	d-e

a: Bailey, 2006; b: Hublin et al., 2017; c: Hershkovitz et al., 2018; d: Martín-Torres et al., 2012; e: Bailey, 2002

SOM Table S3: Detailed list of samples underlying the comparison of dental dimensions summarized in SOM Tables S7 and visualized in Figure 3 and SOM Figure S4.

Groups		Sites	Source
<i>Homo sapiens</i>	Aterian	(Grotte des) Contrebandiers T5, Dar-es-Soltane II H6	a
	early	Jebel Irhoud, Misliya, Qafzeh, Skhul	i-m
	later	Upper Paleolithic individuals from Bacho Kiro, Vindija (Aurignacian), Dolní Věstonice, Mladeč, Pavlov, Predmostí, Abri Pataud, Cap Blanc, Le Peyrat, Grotte de la Balauziere, St. Germain-la-Rivière, Arene Candide, Barma Grande, Grotte des Enfants, Grotta Paglicci, Cisterna, Kent's Cavern, La Rochette, Cro-Magnon, Les Rois, Le Placard; Epipaleolithic individuals from Taforalt, Morocco, and Afalou, Algeria; recent individuals from Australia, India, Europe, Africa, Asia	b-h, n
<i>Homo neanderthalensis</i>	Scladina, Grotte du Bison, La Chaise-de-Vouthon – Abri Bourgeois-Delaunay & Abri Suard, La Quina, Marillac, Monsempron, Moula-Guercy, Shanidar, Amud, Bolomor cave, Palomas 1, Obi-Rakhmat, Le Moustier, Saccopastore, Spy, Tabun, Kůlna, Combe-Grenal, Kalmakia, La Fate, El Salt, Ciota Ciara cave (Monte Fenera), Grotte Boccard, La Ferrassie, Feldhofer Grotte, Taddeo cave, Krapina	b,m,o-aj	
Middle Pleistocene	Europe	Atapuerca-SH, Arago, Petralona, Steinheim, Montmaurin, Pontnewydd	m, ak-ap
	NW Africa	Rabat (Kébibat), Thomas Quarries, Tighennif (Ternifine; isolated)	am, ao

a: Hublin et al., 2012; b: Voisin et al., 2012; c: Frayer, 1978; d: Vallois & Billy 1965; e: Patte, 1968; f: Blanchard et al 1974; g: Trinkaus et al 2011; h: Violette et al 2015; i: Hublin et al., 2017; j: Hershkovitz et al., 2018; k: Vandermeersch, 1981; l: Tillier, 2014; m: Wolpoff, 1971; n: personal communication with S. E. Bailey; o: Wolpoff, 1979; p: Benazzi et al., 2011; q: Tillier et al., 2013; r: Condemi, 2001; s: Verna, 2006; t: Genet-Varcin, 1976; u: Becam et al., 2019; v: Garralda et al., 2020; w: Coulonges et al., 1952; x: Smith et al., 2006; y: Hlusko et al., 2013; z: Harvati et al., 2013; aa: Trinkaus, 1983; ab: Sakura, 1970; ac: Arsuaga et al., 2012; ad: Pinalla & Trinkaus, 2017; ae: Glantz et al., 2008; af: Jelinek 2012; ag: Villa & Giacobini, 1996; ah: Garralda et al., 2014; ai: Maureille et al., 2008; aj: Toussaint, 2014; ak: Martín-Torres et al., 2012; al: Bermúdez de Castro et al., 2019; am: Bermúdez de Castro, 1986; an: Compton & Stringer, 2015; ao: Raynal et al., 2010;

SOM Table S4: Sample used in the enamel-dentine junction (EDJ) analyses of upper permanent canines (UC), third premolars (UP3), and fourth premolars (UP4).

Group	Geological Age	Country of Origin	UC	UP3	UP4	Individuals [†]	Abbreviation for Fossil Individuals	Repository/ housing institution of CT scans	
<i>Homo sapiens</i>	Late Pleistocene	Morocco	1	1	1	El'Aliya	El'Aliya	Peabody Museum, Harvard	
		Tunisia	6	6	9				
	Holocene	Egypt	2	4	8			Osteological Collection University of Tübingen (H. Rathmann)	
		Tanzania	1	4	3				
		Germany		9	7				
		later			1	1	La Rochette		LR
			France			1	Abri Pataud	AP	Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle (MNHN; A. Balzeau, D. Grimaud-Hervé)
	Aterian	Late Pleistocene	Morocco		1	1	Dar-es-Soltane II H6	DS6	Max Planck Institut für evolutionäre Anthropologie (MPI EVA; J.-J. Hublin, P. Gunz)
						1	(Grotte des) Contrabandiers T5	T5	
		Israel		1		Qafzeh 10	QA10	ESRF heritage database (Smith et al., 2010)	
	1	1	1	Qafzeh 15	QA15				
early	Middle Pleistocene	Morocco	1			Jebel Irhoud 21	IR21	Institut National des Sciences de l'Archéologie et du Patrimoine (INSAP; A. Ben-Ncer) & Max Planck Institut für evolutionäre Anthropologie (MPI EVA; J.-J. Hublin, P. Gunz)	
<i>Homo neanderthalensis</i>	Late Pleistocene	France			1	Abri Bourgeois-Delaunay 14	BD14	NESPOS database [‡] (R. Macchiarelli)	
			1	1	1	La Quina H18	LQ18	ESRF heritage database (Smith et al., 2010; C. Verna, C. Schwab)	
			1	1	1	Le Moustier 1	LM	Museum für Naturkunde, Museum für Vor- und Frühgeschichte, Staatliche Museen zu Berlin (E. Dutkiewicz, K. Mahlow)	
	Middle Pleistocene	Croatia		5		Krapina 76, 102, 103, 141, 191	Kr76, Kr102, Kr103, Kr141, Kr191	NESPOS database [‡]	
					5	Krapina 39, 45, 53, 112, 116	Kr39, Kr45, Kr53, Kr112, Kr116		
				8	Krapina 41, 42, 44, 46, 47, 49, 115, 117	Kr41, Kr42, Kr44, Kr46, Kr47, Kr49, Kr115, Kr117			

[†]for Holocene non-fossil individuals only the number of used individuals is provided in columns UC, UP3, and UP4.

[‡]NESPOS database no longer available; Krapina scans now available through NM digital archive

SOM Table S5: Landmark definitions for enamel-dentine junction (EDJ) analyses of upper permanent canines (UC), third premolars (UP3), and fourth premolars (UP4).

Dataset	LM Number in Figures	Landmark Definition
UP3, UP4	1	Mesial fovea or point where the central groove intersects the mesial foveal grooves on the enamel*
	2	Distal fovea or point where the central groove intersects the distal foveal grooves on the enamel [†]
	3	Deepest point on mesial fovea on the EDJ
	4	Deepest point on distal fovea on the EDJ
	5	Tip of the buccal dentine horn (paracone) on the EDJ
	6	Tip of the lingual dentine horn (protocone) on the EDJ
	7	Tip of the dentine horn on the EDJ
UC	8	Most cervical point of the lingual surface at the intersection between the mesial and distal curves on the EDJ. In the case of a present tuberculum dentale, located distally to the tuberculum

[†]following the definitions provided in Gómez-Robles et al. 2011

SOM Table S6: Detailed list of the comparative sample underlying the perikymata analysis of the upper permanent canine (UC). R = right. L = left. NA = undetermined.

Middle Pleistocene Europe [†]		<i>Homo neanderthalensis</i>		later <i>Homo sapiens</i>	
Catalog number	Side	Individuals/Sites	Side	Individuals/Sites	Side
44	L	Genay 1	R	Abri Pataud 22	L
94	NA	Genay 1	L	Aurensan di	R
144	R	Hortus II-III	R	Grotte de Bedeihac	R
163	L	Hortus II-III	L	Estagel 1	R
558	R	Hortus VIII	L	Estagel 1	L
818	L	Hortus VIII	R	Laugerie-Basse	R
825	L	Hortus IX	R	Le Placard	L
955	L	Krapina 36	R	Mas d'Azil	L
958	L	Krapina 37	L	Saulges Mx 1	L
1475	R	Krapina 56	R	Solutré Mx 2	R
1757	L	Krapina 76	R	Solutré Mx 2	L
1758	R	Krapina 103	L	Solutré di	R
1942	L	Krapina 139	L	St. Germain-la-Rivière 10	R
2151	L	Krapina 141	R	St. Germain-la-Rivière 5	R
2207	R	Krapina 142	L	Tarté 1	L
2388	R	Krapina 144	L		
2392	L	Krapina 146	L		
3191	R	Krapina 147	L		
		Krapina Mx 45.1	R		
		Krapina Mx E	L		
		Krapina Mx F	R		
		La Ferrassie II	R		
		La Quina 5	R		
		La Quina 5	L		
		La Quina 17	R		
		Monsempron III	R		
		Saccopastore II	R		
		Saccopastore II	L		
		Vindija 12.5	R		

[†]All teeth from the European Middle Pleistocene are from the site of Sima de los Huesos, Atapuerca, Spain.

SOM Table S7: Comparisons of dental crown dimensions for upper permanent canines (UC), third premolars (UP3), and fourth premolars (UP4). MD = mesiodistal diameter. BL = buccolingual diameter. Measurements in mm and mm², respectively, and values rounded to two decimals. The sample compositions are listed in detail in [SOM Table S3](#).

			El'Aliya	<i>Homo sapiens</i>			<i>Homo neanderthalensis</i>	Middle Pleistocene	
				Aterian	early	later		Europe	NW Africa
UC	MD	N	8.20		13	143	40	26	3
		\bar{X}			8.60	7.82	8.63	8.73	9.13
		σ			0.69	0.59	0.68	0.40	0.40
	BL	N	10.90		13	143	40	26	3
		\bar{X}			9.24	8.69	9.88	9.70	9.93
		σ			0.68	0.66	0.67	0.54	0.12
MD*BL	N	89.38		13	143	40	26	3	
	\bar{X}			79.58	68.28	85.47	84.71	90.72	
	σ			9.98	10.69	11.38	7.03	4.03	
UP3	MD	N	7.70	1	9	192	38	23	4
		\bar{X}		8.40	7.77	7.1	7.83	7.89	8.48
		σ			0.65	0.60	0.68	0.57	0.21
	BL	N	10.30	1	9	192	38	23	4
		\bar{X}		10.00	10.49	9.48	10.75	10.53	11.65
		σ			0.65	0.82	0.64	0.70	0.44
MD*BL	N	79.31	1	9	192	38	23	4	
	\bar{X}		84.00	81.73	67.73	84.51	83.38	98.79	
	σ			10.98	10.82	11.78	11.31	5.81	
UP4	MD	N	8.00	2	9	207	37	23	2
		\bar{X}		8.95	7.18	6.86	7.34	7.65	8.15
		σ		0.35	0.56	0.71	0.84	0.59	0.21
	BL	N	11.10	2	9	207	37	23	2
		\bar{X}		11.50	10.19	9.61	10.35	10.33	11.10
		σ		0.50	0.98	0.81	0.64	0.77	0.14
MD*BL	N	88.80	2	9	207	37	23	2	
	\bar{X}		102.75	73.39	66.32	76.33	79.45	90.48	
	σ		0.45	10.81	12.08	12.86	11.77	3.51	

SOM Table S8: Analyses of variance (ANOVA) of the EDJ datasets for upper canines (UC), upper third (UP3) and fourth premolars (UP4). Sample compositions are provided in [SOM Table S4](#). All values rounded to three decimals. Significant correlations highlighted as bold p-values.

Tooth type	Variable	DoF	R ²	F-value	Z-value	p-value
UC	log (CS)	1	0.172	3.629	2.611	0.033
	group	3	0.165	1.169	0.574	0.293
UP3	log (CS)	1	0.072	2.825	2.034	0.021
	group	3	0.162	2.121	2.280	0.011
UP4	log (CS)	1	0.120	6.187	4.214	<0.001
	group	3	0.124	2.126	2.582	0.007

SOM Table S9: Perikymata counts by decile for the upper permanent canine (UC). The sample compositions are listed in detail in [SOM Table S6](#). Measurements values rounded to one decimal.

		El'Aliya	Middle Pleistocene Europe	<i>Homo neanderthalensis</i>	later <i>Homo sapiens</i>
Decile 5	N		9	17	10
	\bar{x}	15.0	14.3	12.6	15.2
	σ		2.5	2.3	2.3
	range		11-17	9-17	11-19
Decile 6	N		14	21	10
	\bar{x}	17.0	15.5	14.0	17.3
	σ		3.5	2.7	2.3
	range		10-21	9-20	14-21
Decile 7	N		17	26	14
	\bar{x}	20.0	17.9	15.3	19.2
	σ		3.5	3.0	2.2
	range		12-23	11-23	16-23
Decile 8	N		16	28	15
	\bar{x}	22.0	20.6	17.1	26.5
	σ		3.6	2.4	4.6
	range		14-26	14-24	20-35

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